

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR IMPROVING LABOR EDUCATION IN A MODERN FAMILY

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Abstract: The purpose of the article is to study the pedagogical conditions for the successful implementation of labor education in a modern family. In a modern family, the tasks of developing moral traits in a child must be solved in the process of labor education.

Key words: labor education, scientific and technological progress, social community, social relations, social institutions, personal status, structure of society.

In the conditions of scientific and technological progress and the transition of the economy of our state to market relations, the choice of sphere of labor activity becomes especially problematic. With the advent of market relations, a labor market also arises. Self-supporting state enterprises, collective and state farms, cooperators and tenants will hire the most qualified and capable of performing labor functions. In this situation, labor education in the family is a very important task today. That is, instilling in children a hard work ethic and a desire to work, especially in urban families where, due to the prevailing circumstances, children, not being accustomed to work from a very early age, do not have a hard work ethic.

Labor is a conscious, expedient, creative activity of a person, aimed at satisfying his material and spiritual needs, developing his physical and spiritual essential powers, as well as moral qualities.

The content of labor consciousness is production experience: professional knowledge, skills and abilities. It also includes personal interest and entrepreneurship, understanding of the social significance of personal duty and everyone's responsibility for the results of work, an active and creative attitude towards it; the worker's desire to establish the principle of social justice; emotional, moral and aesthetic attitude towards work.

A developed labor consciousness contributes to the formation in a person of hard work, his moral traits, the ability to correlate his needs and the forms of their satisfaction with the volume and quality of personal work.

The pedagogical condition for improving labor education in a modern family is the systematic work activity of the child at home, which will contribute to the development in the child himself of such personal qualities as responsibility, accuracy, respect for the work of others, which will develop a labor consciousness in him, will contribute to the emergence of hard work, and as a consequence of the skills and abilities needed in future work.

A child should always be faced with some kind of work task that he can solve. This task can be either short-term or long-term. For example: you can instruct a child to keep a certain room clean for a long time, but how he will do this - leave it to him to decide and be responsible for the decision. This will give him an organizational task. Consequently, the more complex and independent the work task, the better it will be in pedagogical terms.

Hard work is the result of labor education, training and professional guidance and acts as a personal quality that is characterized by a strong need-motivational sphere, a deep understanding of the great educational power of labor of knowledge and belief, the ability and desire to conscientiously perform any necessary work and show strong-willed efforts in overcoming those obstacles that occur in the course of work.

According to Kharlamov I.F. hard work includes the following structural moral components:

- a) the need for creative work activity and its healthy social and personal motives
- b) understanding the benefits of work for oneself and conviction of its moral charity;
- c) the presence of labor skills and abilities and their constant improvement;
- d) a sufficiently strong will of the individual.

Socially useful work forms moral traits. Labor education is one of the main ways of personality formation. A.S. Makarenko expressed this idea in a clear and precise form:

“Correct education cannot be imagined as education without labor. In educational work, work should be one of the most basic elements.”

The main conditions for labor education are to include children in feasible and useful work already at preschool age.

Of course, within the boundaries of the family it is difficult to give a child such a labor education, which is usually called qualification. The family is not equipped to obtain good specialized qualifications; A boy or girl will receive qualifications in any public organization: at a school, at a factory, at an institution, at courses. In no case should a family strive for qualifications in one specialty or another.

But parents should not think at all that family upbringing has nothing to do with obtaining a qualification.

It is family labor training that is most important for a person's future qualifications. The child who has received the correct labor education in the family will later undergo his special training with great success.

In the same way, parents should not think that by labor we mean only physical labor, muscular work. With the development of machine production, physical labor is gradually losing its former importance in human social life. Man is becoming more and more the owner of large, organized mechanical forces; now more and more, not physical, but mental forces are required of him: management, attention, calculation, ingenuity, resourcefulness, acumen. In their family, parents should raise not a scrap workforce, but an intellectual, creatively thinking working person.

We should not think that labor education in the family means only physical education. Labor education in the family combines both physical and mental labor. In both cases, the important aspect is, first of all, the organization of labor effort, its real human side.

To develop a conscientious attitude towards work, stimulating the child is of great importance.

Social recognition plays a significant role in shaping students' positive attitude towards work. This lifts the child's mood and reveals his conscious attitude towards the need to work for the common good.

Adult approval is especially important when a child experiences inner satisfaction from the knowledge that he has achieved success in completing a work task. Equally important - if

necessary - is reprimand. In the process of pedagogically organized work, the correct moral and aesthetic assessment of each individual is developed.

In a market economy with its strict requirements for the general labor and professional qualities of an employee, undeniable advantages are given to those who are accustomed to work conscientiously, to perform any work efficiently and on time, and have the required knowledge and skills for this.

The meaning of labor is revealed through the system of incentives. These are, firstly, material incentives that encourage a person to work as a source of consumption;

secondly, moral incentives that focus on work as a means of social self-affirmation, its claims to a certain social status, to approval from the team, society;

thirdly, creative incentives that promote interest in activities that are attractive and interesting in themselves;

fourthly, moral incentives, thanks to which a person works, creating the prerequisites for the well-being of other people, society as a whole, and the spiritual development of the worker's personality.

The biggest challenge for parents is how to deal with so-called lazy children. Laziness develops in a child due to improper upbringing, when from a very young age parents do not instill in the child energy, do not teach him to overcome obstacles, do not arouse in him interest in the family household, do not instill in him the habit of work and the habits of those pleasures that work always delivers. There is only one way to combat laziness: gradually drawing the child into the field of work, slowly arousing his interest in work.

The quality of work should be of the most decisive importance: high quality must always be demanded, demanded seriously. There is no need to vilify a child for bad work, shame him, or reproach him. You need to simply and calmly say that the work was done unsatisfactorily, that it should be redone or corrected, or done again. At the same time, it is never necessary to do the work for the child by the parents themselves; only in rare cases can it be possible to do a part of the work that is clearly beyond the child's strength. Makarenko strongly discourages the use of any rewards or punishments in the labor field. The work task and its solution should in themselves give the child such satisfaction that he experiences joy. Recognition of his work as good work should be the best reward for his work. But even such verbal approval should never be abused; in particular, you should not praise the child for the work done in the presence of your acquaintances and friends. Moreover, there is no need to punish a child for bad work or for work not done. The most important thing in this case is to ensure that the work is completed.

If the need or interest is not enough to make the child want to work, you can use the request method. The request differs from other types of appeal in that it provides the child with complete freedom of choice.

A request is the best and gentlest way of addressing, but you should not abuse the request. The request form is best used in cases where you know well that the child will gladly fulfill your request. If you have any doubt about this, use the form of an ordinary order, calm, confident, businesslike. If from a very young age your child correctly alternates requests and instructions, and especially if you arouse the child's personal initiative, teach him to see the need for work himself and carry it out on his own initiative, there will be no breakthroughs in

your instructions. Only if you have started the business of education, you will sometimes have to resort to coercion.

Coercion can be different - from a simple repetition of an order to a sharp and demanding repetition. In any case, you should never resort to physical coercion, since it brings the least benefit and causes the child to have an aversion to the work task.

Encouragement - approval, gratitude, awards expressing "+" assessment of the child's activities.

Approval is a simple type of encouragement;

Gratitude is a higher level (reward).

Competition is a method of directing the natural need for competition and priority for the cultivation of qualities necessary for a person and society. Efficiency increases if the tasks are determined by the children themselves.

Punishment - there is still debate on this issue. It should prevent unwanted actions, slow them down, and cause a feeling of guilt towards oneself and other people.

Types of punishment: imposition of additional duties, restriction of certain rights, etc.

When using punishment, you cannot humiliate a child; he must realize the justice of the punishment.

Subjective - pragmatic method - stimulating labor efforts to create conditions when being not hardworking, ill-mannered, etc. becomes unprofitable - economically expensive. Let the child understand that if he behaves this way, he will not be able to earn money in the future.

Having analyzed the psychological and pedagogical literature, we can conclude that a moral attitude towards work is expressed in concern for the interests of the whole society. Knowing the joy of work for people, the joy of work in a team, turns work into a need and serves as a source of moral feelings for the child.

Unity of purpose, teamwork, common experiences, help from comrades in future work in a team will cultivate in the child moral traits such as true friendship, understanding of the interests of the team, and selflessness.

Labor has always been a source of beauty; labor education in the family will allow the child to directly perceive the beauty of labor, feel its transformative power, its attractiveness. The task of labor education in the family is to make the child's work morally significant.

It is very important to prepare a child for work in a team that unites interests, where moral traits develop friendship, mutual assistance, collective creativity in work, establishing interdependence and consistency in work, an atmosphere of high moral and material responsibility, criticism and self-criticism.

Analysis of the materials studied allows us to come to the conclusion that through self-care a child can provide effective assistance to parents by taking on some of the household chores. This instills in the child initiative, independence in work, conscious discipline, efficiency, a sense of responsibility for the assigned work, thriftiness, and the habit of caring for others. All these views develop on the threshold of adolescence and play an important role in future work activity.

Labor is a practical condition for the education of moral qualities, a reliable man-made means of creating subtle matter - the spiritual appearance of a child.

In the process of developing readiness for work, the formation of socio-economic, moral, and aesthetic motives for work occurs in the child's spiritual world.

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